

Empirical Assessment of Urban Green Spaces for the residents: A case of Greater Noida city

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Abstract - The city of Greater Noida was envisioned in 1991-92 with a population of 3.0 Lacs, with an urbanisable area of 5075 Ha in its Phase-1 (up to 2001). In its Phase-2 (up to 2011), the population was envisaged as 7.0 Lacs with an Urbanisable Area of 12,000 Ha. Consequently in its Phase-3 (up to 2021) the population was envisaged as 12.0 Lacs with an Urbanisable Area of 20,000 Ha. But as per census 2011, the population of Gr. Noida was merely over 1.07 Lacs which is phenomenally lesser than the planned estimate. There is also a huge section of population which is only coming up here in search of employment or educational opportunity. This raises the question of liveability and the quality of life for the residents in Greater Noida that people are not flocking in large numbers to this supposedly metropolitan city. Are the residents just following the model of the machine churned living units and losing their sense of individuality? Has the design of its urban-scape become so regimented and predictable, that it fails to create a robust and livable image of this city? Are there enough recreational public spaces for the current and upcoming population thriving in the city?

Considering recreational green spaces for the public at each level, there is a Greater Noida city park- which is a city-level park. Then there is the presence of sector level parks within some prominent sectors, and finally there are neighborhood level parks interspersed with the residential areas and the green belts. This paper carries out an assessment and brings about an analysis of the city level green recreational spaces and areas around the Alpha-I sector with respect to URDPFI guidelines and NBC norms for Greater Noida. This paper aims to outline the potential of the recreational urban green areas of Gr. Noida to revitalize the growth of the city. It also includes an analytical comparison drawn with respect to various aspects observed from two different cities (Greater Noida, Gandhi Nagar) which delineate the potential of their proposal of green cities. The inferences of the comparison will substantiate the outcome of city planning and give references for future possibilities of development.

Key words—Gandhinagar, Greater Noida, Liveability, Revitalisation of city. Urban Green Spaces.